

Translational challenges of biomedical machine learning solutions in clinical and laboratory settings

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Abstract

The ever increasing use of AI methods in biomedical sciences [1] calls for closer inter-disciplinary collaborations that transfer the domain knowledge from life scientists to IT researchers and vice-versa. We highlight two general areas where the use of AI-based solutions designed for clinical and laboratory settings has proven problematic. These are used to demonstrate common sources of translational challenges that often stem from the differences in data interpretation between the clinical and research view, and the unmatched expectations and requirements on the result quality metrics. To conclude, we outline how explicit interpretable inference reporting might be used as a guide to overcome such translational challenges.

1 Introduction

Transfer of machine learning (ML) solutions into clinical and laboratory settings is complicated by many diverse sources of pitfalls. The deficiencies that risk the transferability of such solutions range from reproducibility issues (e.g. data/code/model availability), lack of expert auditing, external validation, to ethical and legal concerns (e.g. informed consent, bias, liability) [2, 3].

Dodging these problems, literature on biomedical ML solutions often focuses on simple evaluation metrics to assess the performance, while disregarding qualities such as adaptability, auditability, and resilience that are key to deploy solutions into real-world settings and prevent data cascades [4].

The growing popularity of ML challenges (and their impact in areas such as biomedical image

analysis [5]) only worsens the issue, promoting the ranking of solutions based on goodness-of-fit metrics that do not reflect phenomenological fidelity, and thus their suitability for clinical or lab settings [6]. Even many peer-reviewed studies lack in data and code availability [7], let alone other aspects concerning external validity such as generalisation to different populations or robustness against concept drift and data shift [8, 9]. Moreover, almost all studies employing ML solutions have been retrospective, despite that only through prospective studies we can properly assess external validity and avoid potential biases arising from *ad-hoc* hyperparameter tuning [9].

Below, we present two case studies illustrating the impact of aforementioned problems in biomedical solutions.

2 Case studies

Chest X-ray image diagnosis of COVID-19.

At the pandemic outset, researchers rushed to develop solutions from crowd-sourced repositories¹ to predict the COVID-19 severity and outcome from chest X-ray (CXR) images. Questionable methods and poor annotation of the datasets spawned a multitude of problems [10–12]. Commonly, the solutions were based on binary or multi-class classification methods that considered a small subset of diseases. However, these solutions assume mutual exclusion of the classes while, in fact, many lung diseases may co-exist. For example, COVID-19 and Tuberculosis share abnormalities such as fibrosis and opacities, and produce a spectrum of pathologies that evolves over time, requiring a combination of tests (e.g. blood, sputum) for their diagnosis [13–

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¹For example: <https://git.io/J0xva>

15]. Attempts to diagnose lung diseases with just CXR images are thus unnecessarily partial and defy the multimodal nature of diagnosis. For all these reasons, regardless of the reported evaluation metric, binary and multinomial classification solutions are rarely suited for real clinical settings, mainly due to unrealistic assumptions about the nature of the predicted phenomena [10, 16].

Notably, high output modality issues are common in biomedical research, and attract possible improvements: Waegeman et al. [17] delved into the problem of multi-target (multivariate) prediction (MTP), providing a unifying view of MTP problems to help researchers on method choice. In a related work, Rauschenberger and Glaab [18] employ multivariate regressions for molecular data.

Disease status detection in cytometry.

Single-cell measurement techniques [19] have enabled gathering of tremendously detailed datasets of millions of cells as individual data-points, offering a direct way to diagnose many forms of cancer and autoimmune diseases. Multitude of approaches appeared to cluster the observations and predict the disease status, suffering from similar deficiencies as the CXR diagnostics despite the ongoing efforts [20–22]. In particular, ML studies are often limited to retrospective data from at most several dozen patients, model the outcome with discrete class assignment, and ignore a plethora of data variability (batch effects and patient variability) that jeopardises their transfer to a general medical setting [23]. After a decade of published research, the problematic re-applicability of the methods has resulted in little adoption even in laboratory practice [7, 24, 25].

Lately, researchers began to utilise advanced dimensionality reduction methods to produce interpretable data visualisations [26]. Despite the unavoidable bias caused by the data dimensionality reduction and their often erroneous use as base data for analyses (e.g. clustering), the visuals have proven surprisingly effective in communicating the complicated modality of the data to experts, who use them to infer cell population presence and relationships quite reliably [27, 28]. Conversely, this gave a novel use where the interpretable but likely misleading visualisation could be used for quick quality control of the ML algorithm output [29],

where the visualisation may be intuitively used to detect problematic inter-sample variability and failures of clustering or population identification.

3 Discussion

These two use-cases show that despite the common pitfalls may be repeatedly observed across the translational medicine landscape, there are viable research directions that may alleviate the problems. These may eventually give a reliable methodology for integrating advanced ML solutions into the laboratory and clinical practice.

The most problematic feature of the ML studies that impedes adoption is the representation of the diagnostic as a multi-class assignment problem that carries almost no resemblance to the clinical reality. Moreover, proper modelling of the ML output, e.g. as multi-modal feature systems or fuzzy assignments, may also alleviate the issues.

As a guideline, sufficient metadata must be available to model such a rich space of possible outcomes. Interpretation of the dataset guided by rich metadata also improves latent space representations [27], which is, in turn, a key property for training better predictors. Metadata availability may further alleviate the common problem of practitioners who face situations where they need to “work with what they have”, often lacking parts of measurements and the “selective capability” of laboratories to discard poor quality samples, because of the data acquisition limits in clinical settings [4].

We observed the shift of utilisation of the ML-based visualisation techniques, from serving as a likely biased base for analysis to a valid resource for quick validation of the results of other ML methods. Despite bringing no improvement for actual ML methods, this enables safer utilisation of the existing ML approaches in the clinical settings [30], where trained personnel may quickly recognise a classification problem and act accordingly, thus increasing the tolerance of the deployment to classifier errors and, collaterally, improving the compliance with existing regulations. In the long term, we expect that similar utilities may be developed for many other kinds of ML algorithms, potentially improving adoption of existing methods and driving the long-term shift towards the wide adoption of translational ML solutions.

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